

Tuning Fluorescence and Singlet Oxygen Generation in Heavy-Atom-Free BODIPYs through Charge-Transfer State Modulation

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Abstract:

Heavy-atom-free photosensitizers are increasingly recognized as versatile alternatives to traditional heavy-atom systems, which often exhibit shortened triplet lifetimes, poor photostability, and limited biocompatibility. Donor-acceptor architectures, particularly compact BODIPY dyads with orthogonal subunits, efficiently promote intramolecular charge-transfer states that facilitate intersystem crossing (ISC) without relying on heavy atoms. In this study, we demonstrate that ISC and excited-state deactivation pathways in compact heavy-atom-free BODIPY dyads can be systematically modulated beyond simple *meso*-donor variation through the combined effects of core alkylation, boron-centered electron-withdrawing substitution, and solvent polarity. This study integrates the structural design and synthesis of a small family of BODIPY dyads with selected substitution patterns, photophysical characterization in solvents of

varying polarity, transient absorption spectroscopy, cyclic voltammetry for redox profiling, and DFT/TD-DFT calculations to explore the electronic structure and excited-state properties of these BODIPY derivatives. Our findings indicate that careful *meso*-donor selection, coupled with systematic core alkylation and boron electron-withdrawing substitution, produces heavy-atom-free BODIPY photosensitizers with tunable photophysical and electrochemical properties, exhibiting solvent- and substitution-dependent behaviors, ranging from high fluorescence with negligible ISC, to dominant ISC with minimal fluorescence, or a balanced contribution of both functions. These results provide a mechanistic framework for engineering heavy-atom-free BODIPY photosensitizers with tunable fluorescence and reactive oxygen generation, opening new opportunities for the development of tailored molecular platforms for bioimaging, photodynamic therapy, and related photonic applications.

Keywords: BODIPYs, Heavy-atom-free photosensitizers, Spin-orbit charge-transfer intersystem crossing, Donor-acceptor systems, Fluorescence tuning, Singlet oxygen generation, Boron substitution, Solvent effects, Transient absorption spectroscopy

Introduction:

The development of efficient photosensitizers (PSs) is central to applications ranging from photodynamic therapy to photocatalysis. Traditionally, enhancing the intersystem crossing (ISC) efficiency of fluorophores has relied on the introduction of heavy halogen (Br, I)¹⁻⁴ or transition metal (Ru, Re, Ir, Pd, Pt)⁵⁻⁸ atoms into the molecular structure to enhance spin-orbit coupling (SOC) and facilitate the population of the triplet manifold.⁹⁻¹¹ While this strategy induces triplet-state population ($S_1 \rightarrow T_n$) and enables efficient singlet oxygen generation, it simultaneously enhances ISC back to the ground state ($T_1 \rightarrow S_0$), leading to markedly shortened triplet lifetimes and thus limiting the overall efficacy of photosensitization. Moreover, the addition of heavy atoms to chromophores diminishes their photostability and water solubility, increases dark cytotoxicity, and raises environmental concerns, thereby motivating the search for alternative strategies.

Heavy-atom-free (HAF) photosensitizers have emerged as promising alternatives for overcoming these limitations. Various HAF design strategies have been explored, including: (i) organic donor-acceptor motifs that facilitate the formation of charge-transfer (CT) excited states, enabling spin-

orbit charge-transfer ISC (SOCT-ISC) and thermally activated delayed fluorescence (TADF)-inspired triplet harvesting;^{10,12–14} (ii) twisted π -conjugated systems, in which reduced molecular symmetry and enhanced spin-vibronic coupling promote singlet-triplet interconversion;^{14–17} (iii) aggregation-enhanced ISC (AEI) systems, where restricted intramolecular motions in the aggregated or confined state suppress non-radiative decay and favor efficient triplet generation;^{10,18,19} and (iv) fullerene-chromophore hybrids, in which fullerenes serve as highly effective spin converters and triplet-state acceptors.^{19,20} These approaches offer increased structural versatility and cost-effective synthesis, promoting long-lived triplet states suitable for photosensitization, and expanding the scope of practical applications of photosensitizers across diverse photochemical and biomedical contexts.

Among the HAF strategies for triplet-state formation, donor-acceptor architectures stand out for their efficiency. Accordingly, compact BODIPY-based dyads incorporating mutually orthogonal donor and acceptor subunits provide a clear illustration of this design principle.²¹ Although substituents at various positions of the BODIPY core have been explored, linking the donor and acceptor through the *meso* position is the most common, as excitation induces a pronounced redistribution of electronic density at this site, rendering it highly sensitive to photophysical tuning.^{22–25} A wide range of electron-donating groups, including anthracene,²⁶ pyrene,²⁷ perylene,²⁸ coumarin,²⁹ perylenebisimide,³⁰ phenanthroimidazole,³¹ phenothiazine,³² enamine,³³ electron-rich phenyl substituents,^{34,35} and additional BODIPY units³⁶ have been employed to modulate photophysical properties. Careful donor selection allows the dyad to favor CT states and efficient ISC, while the orthogonal geometry minimizes direct electronic coupling and maximizes triplet formation, providing a versatile platform for the rational design of heavy-atom-free photosensitizers.

While donor-acceptor substitution at the *meso* position has been the most widely exploited strategy for modulating the photophysics of BODIPY-based photosensitizers, other structural positions of the chromophore can critically influence ISC and triplet-state formation in HAF systems. For instance, alkylation at C1 and C7 positions has been shown to enhance fluorescence efficiency by suppressing non-radiative decay pathways, mainly through increased steric hindrance.^{37,38} In contrast, the influence of substitution at the boron center remains largely unexplored, with only a few reports demonstrating donor incorporation or heteroaryl substituents to modulate ISC.^{39,40}

Building on these precedents, this study systematically investigates how *meso* donor strength, core (de)alkylation at C1, C3, C5, and C7, boron-centered electron-withdrawing substituents,

and solvent polarity affect ISC and excited-state dynamics in HAF BODIPY systems. Using 2,4,6-trimethoxyphenyl as a strong *meso* donor and 2,4,6-trimethylphenyl as a weaker analog, we demonstrated that careful tuning of these structural elements preserves fluorescence, while enabling efficient triplet formation. These results provide guidelines for the design of versatile HAF BODIPY photosensitizers with optimized photophysical performance.

Results and Discussion

Design and Synthesis of the New Probes

We designed a series of BODIPY derivatives featuring an electron-donating 2,4,6-trimethoxyphenyl group at the *meso* position, combined with systematic variations at the BODIPY core (C1, C3, C5, and C7) and boron atom, to investigate the impact of these substitutions on fluorescence, ISC, and singlet oxygen ($^1\text{O}_2$) generation efficiencies. This strategy aimed to enhance the photosensitizing performance of the lead compounds **1a-b** (Scheme 1).^{34,35} For comparison, analogous derivatives bearing a weaker donor 2,4,6-trimethylphenyl group at the *meso* position (**4a-b** and **5a-b**) were prepared and characterized as reference compounds (Scheme 1), allowing assessment of the influence of *meso*-donor strength on photosensitizing behavior under otherwise identical structural modifications.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of trimethoxyphenyl-BODIPYs **2a-b** and **3a-b** from **1a-b** and trimethylphenyl-BODIPYs **5a-b** from **4a-b** (red: donor moieties; blue: acceptor moieties).

Starting from two *F*-BODIPYs, one without alkyl substituents (**1a**) and the other bearing methyl groups at positions C1, C3, C5 and C7 (**1b**), we prepared the corresponding 4,4-dicyano-BODIPYs **2a** and **2b** and the 4,4-*O,O'*-oxalato-BODIPYs **3a** and **3b** using procedures that had been previously described by other researchers and by some of us.^{41,42} To the best of our knowledge, these B-substituted compounds have not been reported before. In addition, boron-dicyano BODIPYs **5a-b** with a *meso*-2,4,6-trimethylphenyl substituent were prepared from the corresponding boron-difluoride derivatives **4a-b** (see Supporting Information).

Photophysical Characterization

The absorption and fluorescence spectra of **1a-b**, **2a-b**, and **3a-b** were recorded in a range of solvents including toluene, chloroform, methanol, and phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) (Figure 1). The fluorescence and singlet oxygen quantum yields are shown in Table 1 (additional data in acetone and PBS are provided in Table S1). Furthermore, the kinetics of the excited state were studied using nanosecond and femtosecond transient absorption (TA) spectroscopy. For comparative purposes, the photophysical properties of **4a-b** and **5a-b** are included in the Supporting Information.

Figure 1. Absorption and fluorescence spectra in different solvents (black: toluene, red: chloroform, green: acetone, blue: methanol, and cyan: PBS) of compounds **1a-b**, **2a-b**, **3a-b**.

Table 1. Photophysical properties of BODIPYs **1a-b**, **2a-b**, and **3a-b**: λ_{ab} : Absorption peak wavelength; ϵ : Molar absorption coefficient at peak; λ_{fl} : Fluorescence peak wavelength upon excitation at 490 nm; Φ : Fluorescence quantum yield using a solution of the commercial BODIPY PM567 in EtOH ($\Phi = 0.84$) as reference; τ : Fluorescence lifetime; Φ_{Δ} : Singlet oxygen quantum yield using a solution of 8-MeS-BODIPY in MeOH ($\Phi_{\Delta} = 0.91$) as reference. τ_0^T : Triplet lifetime under nitrogen; k_{q,O_2}^T : Rate constant for triplet state quenching by O_2 .

	Solvent	λ_{ab} (nm)	ϵ_{max} ($M^{-1}cm^{-1}$)	λ_{fl} (nm)	Φ	τ (ns)	Φ_{Δ}	τ_0^T (μs)	k_{q,O_2}^T ($10^{-9}M^{-2}s^{-1}$)
1a	Tol	507.0	61000	522.5	0.85	5.41	0.12	207.5	0.93
	CHCl ₃	507.0	66000	523.5	0.68	5.13	0.25	178.8	0.92
	MeOH	501.5	58000	517.0	0.004	0.39	0.20	66.0	1.63
2a	Tol	512.0	66000	529.0	0.38	3.32	0.28	128.5	0.92
	CHCl ₃	510.5	61000	526.5	0.07	1.76 (94%) 5.52 (6%)	0.75	115.3	0.89
	MeOH	505.5	57000	515.0	0.002	0.03 (78%) 1.17 (14%) 5.43 (8%)	0.07	63.0	1.60
3a	Tol	515.5	56000	530.5	0.51	0.83 (4%) 4.14 (96%)	0.38	217.0	1.27
	CHCl ₃	514.0	53000	528.5	0.03	0.07 (41%) 1.51 (55%) 4.89 (4%)	0.65	188.0	0.88
	MeOH	508.5	49000	517.0	0.013	1.13 (97%) 5.13 (3%)	0.11	56.8	1.50
1b	Tol	509.5	108000	521.0	0.90	5.10	N.A.		
	CHCl ₃	508.5	97000	519.5	0.89	5.85	0.03		
	MeOH	503.5	94000	513.5	0.85	6.52	N.A.		
2b	Tol	509.5	112000	520.5	0.91	5.34	N.A.		
	CHCl ₃	508.0	107000	517.5	0.92	6.13	N.A.		
	MeOH	503.0	102000	512.0	0.34	3.89	0.30	52.5	1.24
3b	Tol	515.0	88000	526.5	0.90	1.04 (3%) 5.71 (97%)	N.A.		
	CHCl ₃	513.0	88000	522.5	0.82	6.48	<0.05		
	MeOH	508.5	84000	518.0	0.19	1.98 (76%) 5.86 (24%)	0.26	56.3	1.29

In compounds **1a-3a**, the absence of methyl substituents at the C1, C3, C5, and C7 positions enhanced the electron-accepting character of the BODIPY core and facilitated intramolecular CT from the trimethoxyphenyl group at *meso* position, an effect that became more pronounced as solvent polarity increased. Accordingly, **1a** displayed a high fluorescence quantum yield in nonpolar toluene, ($\Phi = 85\%$), whereas partial quenching was observed for **2a** ($\Phi = 38\%$) and **3a**

($\Phi = 51\%$), which bear more electron withdrawing groups at boron. In polar solvents, such as acetone and methanol, fluorescence was completely suppressed ($\Phi \leq 1\%$) for all three compounds, consistent with the stabilization of the CT state in polar media. However, an increase in solvent polarity did not result in a continuous increase in singlet oxygen generation. Instead, singlet oxygen generation was maximized in solvents of intermediate polarity, particularly chloroform, with quantum yields ranging from 25% for **1a** to 75% for **2a**, indicating an optimal balance between CT-state population and ISC efficiency. Notably, although $^1\text{O}_2$ generation decreased in both nonpolar and highly polar solvents, it remained moderately efficient even in methanol ($\Phi_{\Delta} = 20\%$ for **1a**, 7% for **2a**, and 11% for **3a**), in sharp contrast to the near-complete suppression of fluorescence.

By contrast, core-alkylated BODIPYs **1b-3b** exhibited a markedly different photophysical behavior. Methyl substitution at the C1, C3, C5, and C7 positions attenuates the electron-accepting character of the BODIPY core, thereby disfavoring CT-state formation despite the presence of the electron-donating *meso* substituent. Consequently, all three compounds displayed intense fluorescence in nonpolar and moderately polar solvents ($\Phi > 80\%$ in toluene and chloroform) and negligible singlet oxygen generation, resembling conventional BODIPYs. In acetone and methanol, however, **2b** and **3b** exhibited moderate $^1\text{O}_2$ generation ($\Phi_{\Delta} = 26\text{--}48\%$) while retaining significant fluorescence ($\Phi = 19\text{--}40\%$). In contrast, the corresponding *F*-BODIPY precursor **1b** remained largely insensitive to solvent polarity, indicating that its electronic structure effectively suppressed CT-state formation and preserved the classical fluorescence-dominated BODIPY photophysics. Importantly, all derivatives bearing the weaker trimethylphenyl donor group at the *meso* position, **4a-b**, **5a-b** (Scheme 1) did not activate CT states in any solvent, regardless of core alkylation or boron substitution, and consistently displayed strong emissive behavior and negligible singlet oxygen production (Figure S1, Table S1).

Accordingly, the photophysical behavior of *meso*-(2,4,6-trimethoxyphenyl) BODIPYs is governed by the subtle interplay between boron substitution and core alkylation. Strong electron-withdrawing groups at the boron center, such as cyano or cyclic oxalate, markedly enhanced singlet oxygen generation in compounds **2a-b** and **3a-b** compared to their fluorinated analogs, whereas core alkylation effectively suppressed CT formation, preserving fluorescence even in polar solvents. This balance is clearly illustrated by the comparison between **1a** and **1b**: while **1a** exhibited moderate singlet oxygen generation ($\Phi_{\Delta} = 12\text{--}35\%$) accompanied by pronounced fluorescence quenching in polar media, **1b** retained high fluorescence quantum yields ($\Phi = 84\text{--}90\%$) with negligible $^1\text{O}_2$ production in all solvents. Together, these results establish *meso*-donor

strength, core alkylation, and boron substitution as key molecular design parameters for the fine-tuning of fluorescence, CT-state activation, and ISC in HAF BODIPY photosensitizers.

To elucidate the excited-state relaxation mechanisms of the investigated compounds, femtosecond TA spectroscopy experiments were performed on compounds **2b**, **2a** and **1a**, in chloroform and methanol (Figure 2). The TA spectra at selected pump-probe delays are shown in Figure S2. These molecules were selected as representative systems because of their distinct substitution patterns and markedly different photophysical behaviors in solvents of contrasting polarity, enabling a detailed assessment of the structure-property-environment relationships.

Figure 2. Decay-associated spectra (DAS) of **2b**, **2a**, and **1a** in chloroform, and methanol. The shaded area covers the spectral region affected by the pump-laser-induced scattering.

The TA spectra of **2b** in chloroform (Figure S2a) are characterized by three dominant features: an excited-state absorption (ESA) band at 350-450 nm, ground-state bleach (GSB) at 450-500 nm, and stimulated emission (SE) at 520-600 nm. The close correspondence of these features with the steady-state absorption (GSB) and emission (SE), as well as with the TA features of pristine BODIPY,⁴³ indicates the exclusive involvement of the locally excited (LE) S_1 state. A global analysis of the TA data revealed three kinetic components, with the slowest component dominating the overall spectral response. The distribution of the pre-exponential factors resulting from this analysis is shown in the decay-associated spectra (DAS) in Figure 2a. The first two components ($\tau_1 = 2.6$ ps and $\tau_2 = 39$ ps) are ascribed to vibrational energy redistribution and relaxation processes, whereas the slowest component ($\tau_3 = 4.3$ ns) is assigned to radiative decay to the ground state via fluorescence. The absence of evidence for significant CT or triplet-state populations indicates that the excited-state behavior of **2b** in CHCl_3 is characteristic of conventional BODIPY dyes widely used as highly fluorescent probes. These findings are consistent with the steady-state photophysical properties of **2b**, which exhibits a high fluorescence quantum yield ($\Phi = 92\%$) and negligible singlet oxygen generation.

The TA spectra of **2b** in MeOH (Figure S2b) reveal, in addition to the ESA, GSB, and SE bands, a distinct band at approximately 570 nm, associated with the formation of a CT state.⁵¹ The corresponding DAS (Figure 2b) displays a more complex kinetic behavior than that in chloroform, requiring four components for an adequate global fit. The two fastest components (τ_1 and τ_2) do not contribute to GSB recovery, ruling out important internal conversion (IC) on the picosecond timescale. The CT state is formed within the first 46 ps after excitation. The singlet excited state population, comprising both LE and CT character, decayed with a time constant of 3.1 ns, concomitant with ground-state recovery and ISC to the triplet manifold. Analysis of the GSB decay in the 470-480 nm region indicates that approximately one-third of the excited-state population undergoes triplet-state formation, which is in good agreement with the measured singlet oxygen quantum yield ($\Phi_\Delta = 30\%$, Table 1).

The TA spectra of **2a** in CHCl_3 (Figure S2c) provide unambiguous evidence for the rapid population of a CT state within the 10 ps-1 ns time window, followed by the emergence of triplet-state signatures at longer delay times. Consistently, the DAS feature in the 500-600 nm region (Figure 2c) reveals CT-state formation within the first 46 ps. The absence of the GSB contribution in component τ_3 indicates that the CT state predominantly decays to the triplet manifold with a lifetime of 1.7 ns, resulting in a high triplet quantum yield. Although the singlet excited state exhibits a relatively long lifetime (1.7 ns), its pronounced CT character suppresses

radiative decay, accounting for the low fluorescence efficiency. This photophysical scenario is fully consistent with the steady-state data (Table 1), which show weak emission ($\Phi = 7\%$) and efficient singlet oxygen generation ($\Phi_{\Delta} = 75\%$).

The TA spectra of **2a** in MeOH (Figure 2d) show the very rapid formation of the CT state, with only a minimal excited-state population persisting beyond 100 ps. Consistently, the DAS of **2a** in MeOH (Figure 2d) shows a rapid development of the CT feature at 500-600 nm with a lifetime of 4 ps. This CT state decays within 150 ps, primarily back to the GS, with only a minor fraction (~10%) undergoing ISC to the triplet manifold, as evidenced by the relative magnitude of the GSB band in component τ_4 . This behavior is consistent with the low singlet oxygen quantum yield of this compound ($\Phi_{\Delta} = 7\%$, Table 1).

The DAS in Figure 2e indicates that the kinetics of **1a** in CHCl_3 closely resembles that of **2b** in MeOH (Figure 2b), and shows the formation of a CT state in 55 ps that coexists with the LE state, followed by relaxation through a combination of ISC, fluorescence, and IC on a time scale of 4.5 ns. However, in contrast to **2b** in MeOH, the CT absorption band (500-600 nm) was not evident in the case of **1a**. This can be rationalized by the dominant intensity of the SE band in **1a**, which is consistent with its higher fluorescence quantum yield ($\Phi = 0.68$) compared to that of **2b** in MeOH ($\Phi = 0.34$, Table 1). Therefore, the stronger SE band can mask the positive contribution of the CT band in this spectral region. Despite the different fluorescence yields, the relative magnitude of the GSB band around 475 nm in component τ_4 reveals that, in agreement with the data in Table 1, the triplet quantum yields of both species are also very similar (25%), which indicates that the main differences in their kinetics must be found in the IC channel.

Finally, the TA spectra of **1a** in MeOH (Figure S2f) show, in addition to the ESA, GSB, and SE bands, a clearly distinguishable CT absorption feature at 540 nm, which is observable in the 10-500 ps time interval. Triplet-state absorption was also detected at longer delay times. The DAS of **1a** in MeOH (Figure 2f) shows that the S_1 population evolves on the τ_1 and τ_2 timescales to form the CT state. This state decays within 0.39 ns to the GS (GSB decays with this component) and to the triplet state, with approximately one-quarter of the population undergoing triplet formation, consistent with the measured singlet oxygen quantum yield of 20% (Table 1).

Analysis of the excited-state kinetics showed that CT formation is ultrafast in polar solvents, but becomes significantly slower in nonpolar media, thereby limiting the triplet-state population. At the same time, increasing the solvent polarity stabilizes the CT state and promotes non-radiative decay to the ground state, ultimately compromising both ISC and fluorescence. Therefore, solvent polarity plays a dual and decisive role, governing not only the kinetics of CT-state

formation but also the ultimate fate of the excited state, with direct implications for the rational optimization of photosensitizer performance.

Additionally, the triplet excited states of the probes that exhibited efficient singlet oxygen generation (**1a**, **2a**, **2b**, **3a**, and **3b**) were investigated by nanosecond TA spectroscopy (flash photolysis). All compounds displayed the characteristic TA features of BODIPY chromophores, with intense $T_1 \rightarrow T_n$ bands at 410–420 nm and weaker absorptions above 600 nm (Figure S3). Triplet lifetimes were determined by monitoring the decay at 410–420 nm in toluene, chloroform, and methanol under nitrogen-, air-, and oxygen-saturated conditions, enabling the assessment of oxygen-dependent triplet quenching and the determination of the corresponding bimolecular rate constants (Table 1, Table S2).

As expected for HAF chromophores, all compounds displayed relatively long triplet-state lifetimes, which were markedly shorter in methanol (52–66 μs) than in toluene and chloroform (115–220 μs ; Table 1 and Table S2), reflecting solvent-dependent deactivation pathways that accelerate non-radiative deactivation in polar media. These long-lived triplet states are highly relevant for photodynamic applications because they increase the probability of collisional energy transfer to molecular oxygen, thereby enhancing singlet oxygen generation. Oxygen-mediated triplet quenching rate constants (k_{q,O_2}^T), extracted from the Stern-Volmer analysis of the triplet lifetimes under nitrogen, air, and oxygen atmospheres, were consistent across the series ($0.88\text{--}1.63 \times 10^9 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$), indicating a predominantly diffusion-controlled collisional quenching process between the photosensitizers and O_2 .

Importantly, the triplet lifetimes observed for the present systems exceed those reported for other heavy-atom BODIPY derivatives and classical photosensitizers such as Rose Bengal and metalloporphyrins, which typically exhibit τ_T values in the range of tens of microseconds under similar conditions.^{44–47} Taken together, these results indicate that the current HAF BODIPYs constitute a particularly efficient and versatile platform for type II photosensitization, combining long-lived triplet states with tunable CT character and favorable oxygen quenching dynamics.

Electrochemical Characterization

Cyclic voltammetry measurements were performed on all compounds to determine their oxidation and reduction potentials (Figure 3). These electrochemical data were used to estimate the corresponding HOMO and LUMO energy levels, providing insights into the electronic structures of the compounds (Table 2).

Figure 3. Cyclic voltammograms of compounds **1a**, **2a**, **3a**, **1b**, **2b** and **3b**.

Table 2. Data obtained from cyclic voltammetry experiments for compounds **1a-b**, **2a-b** and **3a-b** in MeCN solution, referenced to the ferrocene/ferrocenium (Fc/Fc⁺) couple.

Compound	E_{red} (V)	E_{ox} (V)	LUMO (eV)	HOMO (eV)	$\Delta_{\text{LUMO-HOMO}}$ (eV)
1a	-0.88 (R)	1.51 (I)	-3.92	-6.31	2.39
2a	-0.67 (R)	N.A.	-4.13	-	-
3a	-0.67 (R)	N.A.	-4.13	-	-
1b	-1.24 (R)	1.07 (R)	-3.56	-5.87	2.31
2b	-1.04 (I)	1.32 (R)	-3.76	-6.12	2.36
3b	-0.99 (R)	1.44 (R)	-3.81	-6.24	2.43

E_{red} : Reduction potential; E_{ox} : Oxidation potential; (R): Reversible reaction; (I): Irreversible reaction; LUMO, HOMO: Estimated energy of the LUMO and HOMO orbitals calculated using the following widely accepted empirical formulas for potentials referenced to the ferrocene couple (Fc/Fc⁺): HOMO (eV) = $-(E_{\text{ox onset}} + 4.8)$, LUMO = $-(E_{\text{red onset}} + 4.8)$; $\Delta_{\text{LUMO-HOMO}}$: Energy gap between HOMO and LUMO orbitals.

Cyclic voltammetry measurements revealed that the vast majority of the redox processes in our compounds were reversible (Figure 3). The reduction potentials ranged from -0.67 V (**2a** and **3a**) to -1.24 V (**1b**), while the oxidation potentials varied between 1.07 V (**1b**) and 1.51 V (**1a**).

The oxidation potentials for **2a** and **3a** could not be determined, likely because they fall outside the electrochemical window of the solvent we used (MeCN: > 1.9 V).

A clear trend was observed in the electrochemical behavior of both non-methylated (**1a**, **2a**, and **3a**) and methylated (**1b**, **2b**, and **3b**) BODIPY derivatives. In each series, the replacement of BF₂ with B(CN)₂ resulted in a significant positive shift in both the oxidation and reduction potentials, indicating substantial stabilization of the BODIPY-centered frontier orbitals. Further replacement of B(CN)₂ by the oxalato-chelated boron group led to an additional, albeit smaller, positive shift in the redox potentials. Accordingly, the electrochemical data support the effective electron-withdrawing influence that increases in the order BF₂ < B(CN)₂ < B(C₂O₄) within these donor-acceptor BODIPY frameworks. This trend is consistent with the B—N bond distances determined from the corresponding X-ray diffraction structures, as explained below. In contrast, methyl substitution at the C1, C3, C5, and C7 positions increases the electron density of the BODIPY core, leading to more negative reduction potentials (lower electron affinity) and lower oxidation potentials (higher electron-donating ability) in the methylated series (**1b**, **2b**, **3b**) than in the corresponding non-methylated analogs (**1a**, **2a**, **3a**).

Theoretical Calculations

To rationalize the experimentally observed photophysical properties, we carried out density functional theory (DFT) and time-dependent DFT (TDDFT) calculations using the CAM-B3LYP exchange-correlation functional and the cc-pVDZ basis set (see Supporting Information for details). To elucidate the distinct behavior arising from alkylation at the BODIPY core, the presence of different electron-withdrawing groups at the boron atom, and solvent polarity (chloroform vs. methanol), our computational analysis focused on compounds **1a**, **2a**, and **2b**.

At their ground-state optimized geometry, the three systems present a large dihedral angle between the BODIPY core and the trimethoxyphenyl fragment in the *meso* position, from approximately 70° for **1a** and **2a** to a strict perpendicular arrangement for **2b**, indicating weak to vanishing electronic coupling between the two π -systems (Table S3). Vertical excitation calculations at the Franck–Condon region of **1a** and **2a** revealed two nearly degenerate low-lying singlet excited states (S_1 and S_2), with energy gaps of ≤ 0.1 eV, irrespective of solvent polarity (Table 3), while a slightly larger energy gap of 0.37 eV was obtained for **2b**. Analysis of the frontier orbitals involved in the $S_0 \rightarrow S_{1,2}$ transitions shows that one of these excited singlets corresponds to a LE on the BODIPY core, closely resembling the S_1 state of pristine BODIPY (Figures 4, S4, and S5). This transition exhibits a large oscillator strength, which is consistent with

its assignment to the main absorption band. In contrast, the other low-lying singlet displayed a strong CT character, with BODIPY acting as the electron acceptor. The minimal hole-electron overlap leads to weak contribution of the CT transition to the molecular optical activity, which is reflected in its very small oscillator strength.

Figure 4. Frontier molecular orbitals of **1a** involved in the main contributions to S_1 (LE, HOMO→LUMO) and S_2 (CT, HOMO-1→LUMO) excited states computed at the CAM-B3LYP/cc-pVDZ level in chloroform.

In **1a**, our calculations place the LE state below the CT in chloroform, while an increase in solvent polarity results in the quasi-degeneracy of the two states. The substitution of the two fluorine atoms at the boron center with cyano groups in **2a** symmetrically stabilizes both the HOMO and LUMO localized on the BODIPY core, and has almost no effect on the HOMO-1 on the donor group (Table S5). Notably, the computed HOMO-LUMO gaps were in good agreement with the cyclic voltammetry measurements (Table 2). This leads to a marked stabilization of the CT excitation, while the energy of the BODIPY LE state remains nearly unchanged relative to that of **1a** (Table 3). In contrast, the electron-donating character of the four methyl substituents in **2b** significantly destabilized the CT state, placing the LE state well below it (Table 3). Moreover, steric hindrance from the alkyl groups at positions C1 and C7 enforces a nearly perpendicular arrangement between the two molecular fragments, a geometry that, as discussed above, is optimal for CT stabilization. Nevertheless, the electronic effect of the methyl substituents dominated over this structural preference, leading to an overall destabilization of the CT excitation.

Table 3. Singlet state vertical excitation energies (ΔE in eV), character of the transition (LE or CT), oscillator strengths (f), and main orbital contributions computed at the CAM-B3LYP/cc-pVDZ level at the ground-state geometries of **1a**, **2a** and **2b** in chloroform and methanol. H: HOMO; L: LUMO.

System	State	Solvent	Charac.	ΔE	f	Contribution
1a	S ₁	CHCl ₃	LE	2.96	0.545	H→L (97%)
	S ₂		CT	3.06	0.070	H-1→L (93%)
	S ₁	MeOH	CT	2.97	0.108	H-1→L (83%) + H→L (11%)
	S ₂		LE	3.00	0.480	H→L (87%) + H-1→L (10%)
2a	S ₁	CHCl ₃	CT	2.91	0.083	H-1→L (93%)
	S ₂		LE	2.94	0.492	H→L (98%)
	S ₁	MeOH	CT	2.84	0.086	H-1→L (92%)
	S ₂		LE	2.97	0.462	H→L (97%)
2b	S ₁	CHCl ₃	LE	2.88	0.589	H→L (98%)
	S ₂		CT	3.25	0.000	H-1→L (93%)
	S ₁	MeOH	LE	2.91	0.558	H→L (98%)
	S ₂		CT	3.16	0.009	H-1→L (93%)

Structural relaxation on the S₁ and S₂ potential energy surfaces (PESs) of **1a** converged to two distinct minima that retained their differentiated electronic character: one corresponding to a LE on the BODIPY core, and the other to a state with a pronounced CT character. The key structural distinction between these two minima is the dihedral angle between the two fragments (Table S3). For the LE state, the angle decreases relative to the ground state (to ~62°), whereas the CT state acquires an almost perfectly orthogonal arrangement, leading to a vanishing oscillator strength (Table S5). In addition, excited-state relaxation leads to significant changes in the relative energies of the states compared to those in the Franck-Condon regime. In both solvents, the vertical de-excitation gap at the CT minimum (the energy difference between the CT and GS at the CT relaxed geometry) was lower than that at the LE minimum (Table S5), which is consistent with the positions of the emission bands (Figure 1).

The population of the triplet manifold is expected to occur primarily via spin-orbit coupling (SOC)-mediated ISC from the CT minimum, as geometric relaxation proceeds much faster. In contrast, ISC from the LE state cannot effectively compete with radiative decay, as previously observed for pristine BODIPY^{24,48}. Calculations at the CT minimum revealed two energetically close triplet states (Table S6): T₂, corresponding to the triplet CT state, and T₃, corresponding to a local BODIPY excitation (reminiscent of the T₂ state in the parent molecule). According to El-Sayed's rule^{49,50}, the SOC between the two CT states is very small (< 0.1 cm⁻¹), whereas the SOC with T₃ is more than an order of magnitude larger, a value considered significant for organic molecules.^{50,51} On this basis, i.e., small singlet-triplet gap and strong SOC, we tentatively assigned the ¹CT→T₃(LE) channel as the dominant ISC pathway in **1a**. This interpretation also rationalizes the experimental observation that the highest triplet yield (monitored via singlet oxygen generation) was achieved in solvents of intermediate polarity. A certain degree of polarity is

necessary to stabilize the CT state; however, excessive stabilization increases the energy gap with T_3 while reducing that with the ground state, thereby decreasing the ISC rate and simultaneously enhancing the non-radiative decay to the ground state.

Calculations at the ground-state geometry of **2a** in chloroform and methanol place the CT state below the LE state, and excited-state geometry optimizations converge exclusively to the singlet CT minimum (the LE minimum could not be located in either solvent). These results are consistent with the very low fluorescence efficiencies that were observed experimentally. As in **1a**, we identified $^1\text{CT} \rightarrow T_3(\text{LE})$ as the most likely dominant channel for ISC (Table S6). Despite a small increase in the SOC with higher solvent polarity, the $^1\text{CT}-T_3$ energy gap increased by approximately 0.1 eV, indicating a reduced ISC rate in methanol (by approximately two orders of magnitude). Therefore, we tentatively attribute the simultaneous lack of fluorescence and triplet population of **2a** in methanol to the stabilization of the CT state, which inhibits emission from the LE state and notably reduces the ISC efficiency by increasing the gap with T_3 .

In contrast, upon relaxation of the low-lying singlets of **2b** on their respective PES, we were unable to obtain the CT minimum and the system systematically converged to the LE minimum in both solvents. This state exhibits a large oscillator strength (Table S5). These results rationalize the comparatively higher fluorescence and lower singlet oxygen quantum yields of **2b** (and analogously of **1b** and **3b**) in weakly polar solvents (e.g., chloroform) and would explain the need for highly polar solvents (e.g., methanol) to promote CT population and subsequent ISC.

In summary, the combined experimental and computational analyses revealed that the photophysical behavior of the studied BODIPY derivatives was governed by a subtle interplay between the substitution at the carbon backbone (H vs. methyl), electron-withdrawing strength of the boron substituents, and polarity of the solvent (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Schematic representation of the different possible pathways available after excitation of the studied BODIPY derivatives upon chemical substitution and solvent polarities.

Substitution at C1, C3, C5, and C7 positions plays a key role in controlling CT activation. The hydrogen-substituted series (**1a-3a**) more readily enables CT state formation, whereas the methyl-substituted derivatives (**1b-3b**) hinder CT due to their stronger electron-donating character and the associated electronic destabilization of the CT configurations. As a result, the methylated compounds generally retain stronger fluorescence and reduced CT involvement.

The nature of the boron substituents ($F_2 < (CN)_2 < C_2O_4$) modulates the acceptor strength and, thus, the stabilization of the CT states. Weakly withdrawing substituents (F_2 , **1a** and **1b**) favored the LE states, leading to high fluorescence efficiencies. Increasing electron-withdrawing strength ($(CN)_2$ in **2a** and **2b**) promoted partial CT character, enabling ISC and the population of long-lived triplet states, which are effective for singlet oxygen generation. In the strongest case (oxalato, **3a** and **3b**), CT states become highly stabilized.

Solvent polarity further tunes this balance. In nonpolar environments, LE states dominate and fluorescence is efficient. As solvent polarity increases, CT states are stabilized, and in intermediate cases this stabilization can facilitate ISC, thereby enhancing triplet formation and photodynamic activity. However, when CT stabilization becomes too strong (especially for **2a** and **3a** in polar solvents), non-radiative decay to the ground state dominates, leading to fluorescence quenching and reduced triplet yields.

X-Ray Crystallography

Single crystals of all compounds in the series were successfully grown from CH_2Cl_2 /hexane solutions, and their solid-state structures were elucidated using single-crystal X-ray diffraction (Figure S6, Tables S7-S12). The crystal structure of **1a** had been previously reported³⁵ and was also independently determined in this work. For compounds **2a** and **3a**, two inequivalent molecules were observed in the asymmetric unit, with **3a** crystallizing as a dichloromethane solvate. Compounds **1a**, **2a**, **2b**, and **3a** crystallized in the triclinic crystal system (space group $P-1$), compound **1b** in the monoclinic system (space group $C2/c$), and compound **3b** in the orthorhombic system (space group $Pbcn$). The solid-state structures revealed the expected quasi-orthogonal spatial orientation of the *meso*-aryl and dioxaborolane (in **3a** and **3b**) rings relative to the central dipyrromethene chromophore (Table 4), consistent with the steric repulsion caused by the ortho-methoxy groups and the tetrahedral coordination geometry of the boron atom of the dioxaborolane moiety in both **3a** and **3b**. The measured dihedral angles between the corresponding least-squares mean plane of the BODIPY core and the *meso*-phenyl ranged from 64.9° to 82.4°. As previously discussed, these dihedral angles are essential for

enabling efficient SOCT-ISC. The measured dihedral angles between the corresponding least-squares mean plane of the BODIPY core and dioxaborolane ring are nearly orthogonal, being from 86.6° to 89.8°. In addition, the shorter B—N bond lengths observed for the more electron-withdrawing boron substituents (Table 4) are consistent with the enhanced B—N bond stabilization and increased delocalization/aromatic character of the BODIPY core, in agreement with the trends observed for the redox potentials. This interpretation is supported by prior experimental and computational studies on B-substituted BODIPYs, particularly B(CN)₂ derivatives, which demonstrated that B—N bond contraction, reduced charge density at boron, lower bond-length alternation, and increased aromaticity are correlated.⁵²

Table 4. Selected structural data for BODIPYs **1-3a,b** in the crystalline form.

Compounds:	1a	2a	3a	1b	2b	3b
d(B—N/N') ^a (Å)	1.552	1.535, 1.538	1.515, 1.530	1.545	1.535	1.525
	1.552	1.531, 1.543	1.516, 1.530	1.549	1.536	1.530
<(N ₂ B/BO ₂) ^b	-	-	88.2° 86.6°	-	-	89.8°
<(BDP/Aryl) ^c	72.7°	72.6° 79.7°	64.9° 74.4°	82.4°	73.3°	79.7°

^a B—N bond length; ^b Dihedral angle between the least squares mean plane of the boradiazaindacene (C₉BN₂) system and the plane of the B(C₂O₄) group; ^c Dihedral angle between the least squares mean plane of the boradiazaindacene (C₉BN₂) system and the phenyl ring.

Conclusions

The combined experimental and theoretical results establish a clear structure-photophysics-environment relationship in this family of *meso*-(2,4,6-trimethoxyphenyl)-BODIPY derivatives. By systematically modulating core alkylation and boron substitution, we demonstrated that even minor structural changes are sufficient to shift the balance between fluorescence emission and ISC to triplet states, enabling singlet oxygen generation quantum yields of up to 75% in these HAF systems. Our results show that electron-withdrawing substituents at boron promote the population of a CT state, which facilitates SOCT-ISC to the triplet manifold, leading to efficient singlet oxygen generation. In contrast, alkylation at the C1, C3, C5, and C7 positions reduces the electron-accepting character of the BODIPY core, attenuating CT formation and boosting fluorescence. The orthogonal arrangement between the *meso* electron-donating aryl group and

the BODIPY core, as confirmed by single-crystal X-ray diffraction, plays a critical role in enabling efficient SOCT-ISC in these systems.

The central conclusion of this study is that the balance between fluorescence and triplet formation is governed not only by molecular substitution but also by the impact of solvent polarity on the relative energetics and fate of the LE and CT states. In weakly polar media, CT formation is slower and less favorable, which limits the triplet-state population. However, in highly polar media, the CT state is significantly stabilized and can become energetically dominant. Under these conditions, fluorescence is suppressed, but ISC does not necessarily improve, as excessive CT stabilization promotes non-radiative decay to the ground state and may widen the energy gap between the emissive/CT singlet and relevant triplet states. Therefore, the highest photosensitization efficiency is not achieved at maximum CT stabilization, but rather when the LE and CT states are optimally balanced to favor productive ISC over both radiative decay and direct non-radiative deactivation. Flash photolysis studies demonstrated that all compounds exhibited long-lived triplet states that facilitated efficient singlet oxygen generation through collisional quenching, a potent type II photodynamic mechanism.

DFT and TDDFT calculations provide a consistent framework for rationalizing these photophysical trends, highlighting the delicate interplay between LE and CT states, their modulation by chemical substitution and solvent polarity, and the role of SOC between CT singlets and nearby triplets in governing ISC pathways. The computational results closely aligned with the experimental observations, underscoring the predictive power of molecular design strategies in tailoring photophysical properties.

More broadly, this study demonstrates that efficient HAF photosensitization is not merely dictated by the presence of CT states, but rather by the precise tuning of the LE/CT balance through molecular structure and environment. In this family of dyes, key design parameters such as *meso*-donor strength, core alkylation, boron substitution, and solvent polarity play a crucial role in controlling fluorescence, triplet formation, and singlet oxygen generation. These findings offer a mechanistic framework for the rational development of enhanced BODIPY-based photosensitizers for photodynamic therapy, theranostics, and other related photoactive molecular systems.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that supports the findings of this study are available in the supplementary material of this article.

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